

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotation. The given article discusses numerous problems and difficulties in teaching and learning English and provides solutions to them.

Key words: foreign language, problems in language learning activity, educational games, solutions to problems.

Introduction. Now there are more than 600 spoken languages worldwide and they have evolved uniquely and form distinct family trees. English is considered one of the languages belonging to the Germanic family. Teaching foreign languages as a second language and by this instilling common values such as love for homeland, loyalty, national pride and dignity in young generation, is one of the urgent issues of our time.

Over the past 3-4 years in our country, the government is creating opportunities for the young generation to learn foreign languages, especially English, requiring them to get certificates such as IELTS at levels from B1 to C1.

The main goal is for future generations of our homeland to master foreign languages as fluently as their native tongue, which enables them to learn new skills and modern developing technologies without any difficulties. In addition, in this era of XXI century, marked by advancements in information and communication technologies, this has become a common phenomenon that the natural integration of new words, terms and expressions from one language to another. This process not only enhances and develops the language but also shows the need to replace new incoming words with equal terms in Uzbek or find alternative meanings for them.

Teaching English as a second language remains a very challenging task, particularly in contexts where English serves only a limited purpose and this raises the question:” Why are there so many difficulties and problems in learning English? The reasons include the limited vocabulary of today’s youth, low concentration levels, lack of discipline and issues with speech. Additionally, other factors are the insufficient emphasis on English, insufficiently equipped classrooms and shortage of qualified teachers. The role of English language teachers is not only to teach learners or focus on developing their skills in reading, writing, listening and speaking but also to motivate them by fostering a passion, positive attitude and strong motivation towards learning English. However, teachers today face many challenges and obstacles in teaching English. These include:

Disruptive classroom environment- The environment plays a crucial role in teaching and learning language. A distracting classroom atmosphere negatively impacts students and hampers their ability to learn. A suitable and comfortable environment is essential for teaching English. If the environment is not conducive, it disrupts the teaching process. Many teachers face difficulties in managing such unfavorable conditions.

Limited teaching resources- Teaching, not only English but any subject, requires multifaceted resources. Teachers often face the issue of insufficient resources necessary for effective English language learning. Without adequate tools,

teaching and learning become exceedingly difficult. Resources such as speakers, microphones, projectors, computer systems, and other digital devices significantly enhance the teaching and learning experience, making it more effective and engaging.

Overcrowded classrooms.

A high number of students in the classroom causes stress and inconvenience for teachers. Managing large groups demands more effort and dedication. Common issues arising in overcrowded classrooms include:

- Noise that disrupts the teacher.
- Difficulty in managing the students.
- Challenges in engaging all students in the learning process.
- Insufficient resources for all students.

Limited time.

Time is a crucial factor in teaching and learning English. Teachers need adequate time to monitor and instruct their students according to their levels. However, the allocated class time for this subject is often very limited, making it challenging for teachers to deliver lessons effectively within the given timeframe.

Students' dependency on teachers.

Another significant issue teachers face is the over-reliance of students on them. Students often fail to make efforts to learn independently or practice speaking. They frequently turn to teachers for guidance and answers rather than trying to figure things out themselves. Additionally, they do not attempt to correct their sentences or phrases while speaking. This dependency arises because students haven't learned the technical aspects of using different tenses and vocabulary in their speech.

Sometimes students lack interest in learning English and attending lectures. As a result, they try to engage in other activities. Occasionally, they disturb teachers

during lectures by talking to others or doing meaningless tasks. Alongside these challenges and difficulties, there are also solutions. Below are some of the best solutions:

Competitions in class.

Competitions play a vital role in learning English as they motivate students to engage with the language. Activities such as debates, quizzes, and similar contests make learning English more exciting and encourage students to participate and strive to win among their peers. These competitions make teaching easier for teachers. Teachers should organize competitive activities among students to enhance engagement.

Using Multimedia during lectures.

Many English teachers still use outdated and traditional methods in teaching. However, modern devices and gadgets specifically designed for educational purposes can significantly improve English teaching and learning. Teachers should incorporate multimedia tools into their lectures. This makes learning English more interesting and comprehensible for students. For example, visual aids, videos, sounds, and other multimedia elements can help students understand concepts more easily than simply reading from textbooks.

Teaching through games.

Games are activities that highly engage students and play a significant role in education and learning. Many educational games can be played in classrooms to teach English. Games help improve vocabulary. For instance, gap-filling games where students place the missing word in a sentence are excellent for vocabulary development. These activities help students understand different word types, their meanings, and their placement in sentences. Teachers should incorporate games into the classroom to make the learning process more interactive.

Managing class rules and schedules.

Teachers should establish rules and schedules for the class, and students must follow them. Discipline and rules are crucial in learning English. For example, students should turn off their mobile phones, avoid talking with peers, arrive on time, complete their homework, and submit it to the teacher promptly. If students break any of these rules, penalties should be imposed, or their parents should be informed.

Another reason for considering the strategy for the formation of a significant generation as applicable to the current younger generation and ensuring their positive development, in addition to teachers, families, and community attention are needed. Available literature also points to the fact that a person is likely to receive as much as 70 percent of information he or she is ever going to receive in his or her lifetime before he or she is six years of age. This definitively points to the importance of preschool education. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, having convened a meeting on August 16, 2017, identified the measures to achieve the enrollment of 5–6-year-old children to preschool educational establishments at 100 percent. In the wake of this, the Presidential Decree No, “On organizing the activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan” was signed. This decree also was to permit early learning of English in these institutions. According to our ancestors, knowledge acquired in a youthful age is like engraving on a rock. Indeed, this word saying, emphasizes a rather important idea that the earlier education starts, the easier the challenges and difficulties, mentioned above, can be eliminated to help better master the language skills.

Especially, it will be possible to increasing foreign language abilities as far-reaching as first language abilities if this knowledge and these skills are inculcated playing different games and other educational activities. It will be important to note that apart from promoting educational knowledge and skills, educational games also promote physical health of a child, improve his or her confidence and assists in developing social relations with other children. In addition, the challenges described in this article consist of confrontation between the teachers and the young people

overcoming these problems, proposed solutions in this article can fundamentally solve them and improve teaching and learning processes.

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